

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHOYOMBO****FIRST NAME: VICTORIA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

STEPS TO WRITING AN OUTSTANDING RESEARCH PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

The hallmark of a Ph.D. student is the ability to conduct research and literature review and answer research questions concisely. It is, therefore, important that the student's first introduction is "how to write a research paper." This paper discusses in details, the steps to follow to successfully write a research paper.

The student must be able to identify a research question, discuss relevant literature reviews, reference previous and relevant authors, and adhere to the expected writing style.

2) WRITING A RESEARCH PAPER

The main objective of any research or academic papers is to answer a research question. To answer the question, you need a main point, referred to as thesis statements, supported with arguments, and examples (EUCLID 2015, 43). As a standard guide, a research paper has three main parts, the introduction, body, and conclusion.

The introduction gives broad opening statements that provide a background or setting for the thesis statement. And summarize the points or main ideas to be discussed in the other paragraphs and we are advised that the introduction should be written after the other paragraphs excluding conclusion have been written. The next set of paragraphs are the body, they provide supporting arguments for the answer stated in the paragraph. Each paragraph is a mini write up with its own topic sentence, arguments, examples and,

emphasis on the relevance of the raised point on the overall argument (EUCLID 2015,4). The body of a research paper is an opportunity for me as a student or writer to discuss my understanding of other papers I have reviewed and how each of them provides support or otherwise for my thesis statement. I must not forget to use relevant examples and quotes as a buttress to my main points. Should there be two or more research questions, the paragraph must be structured to answer each of the questions appropriately. It is expected that the student provides about five points with well-laid out explanation in support of the thesis statement. After the body comes the conclusion which mainly restates the thesis statements, summarize the supporting arguments, state the paper's contribution to research and knowledge, the future directions or any other issues that the writer was not able to address. It is important to note that, no new argument or point be introduced in the conclusion.

The most interesting finding for me is leaving your write up for a while and coming back to review it with a fresh eye (EUCLID 2015, 2), I do this most of the time, but there are times that I am out of time and may barely meet submission deadline, in this case, I go ahead to submit after a quick review of the write up. This point seeks to impress on us the importance of starting your writeup early so that there will be adequate time to review.

3) WRITING AND STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a set of rules or guidelines to document certain elements of writing styles that needs to be consistent. It is often associated with journalism, copy editing, technical and business writing (EUCLID 2015, 52). Many organizations use style guides to ensure consistency in written products especially when there are more than one contributor or author (EUCLID 2015, 52). It will also reflect poorly on the organization if written works reflect the personal styles of writers and not that of the organization.

I am happy to note that Euclid adopts a writing style that is used by major papers and organizations. I have contributed to some national strategic documents but I was not aware of some of these writing conventions. The first module of these course discussed in details the accepted conventions for a good paper.

The key points are using smaller sentences, if a sentence is running into five lines or more, break into smaller sentences (EUCLID 2015, 43). Paragraphs should be about 20 lines, the main sentences should be active, not passive, pay attention to grammar and punctuation and be consistent with the use of language (EUCLID, 43-45). The most important point is to adhere strictly to Euclid's writing style as laid out in the templates.

As a student in Nigeria, the official language is British English, however, most of our books and computer devices are from the US. Over time, there has been an increasing acceptance of the US English, as a writer, I find myself writing with a mix of both styles especially spellings. Having difficulty separating the two. The default language on my laptop is US English; I would love to maintain the UK English in my write-up that may, however, be a challenge.

4) UNDERSTANDING THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN BRITISH AND AMERICAN ENGLISH

I never truly understand the difference between the British and American English, and I often assumed it was restricted to spellings and pronunciation. The text provided examples of other instances such as date, use of punctuation marks, grammar, syntax, colloquial expression and others. As a writer, one needs to pay attention and be consistent with one's choice. Many of the common language editing software are default to using the US English, including the popular Microsoft word, except you have adequate knowledge of computer settings you may be unaware that you can change to your preferred choice. Although in Nigeria, the accepted form is British English, it is common to see articles using spellings and expressions from both styles interchangeably.

5) REFERENCING

Referencing is an integral part of academic writing. It ensures that writers acknowledge the contribution of others to the information shared. Plagiarism occurs "when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author." (EUCLID 2015, 9-13). Euclid recommends that we use the Turabian style of referencing also referred to as the Chicago style. A detailed explanation and style guide was also provided to guide students who may be unfamiliar with the style.

Most importantly, as a writer, I need to understand when to cite or not cite a reference, when to use a block quotation or in-text quotation. The use of capitalization, when to write numbers in words, how and when to use abbreviations, use of endnotes and footnotes and the arrangements of names and dates in the bibliography. Finally, the most important message is to be consistent in our choice of referencing style.

6) EUCLID WRITING TEMPLATE

One of the key things I learned from this period is the importance of adhering to the school's template for response and major papers. The templates are very similar to writing conventions for articles and by consistent use, the student will develop proficiency in academic writing. The academic writing course will ensure that students achieve the course outcome and become proficient in academic writing and referencing.

7) CONCLUSION

Period one (1) learning was an introduction to academic writing and serves mostly as a reminder and reinforcement of what I had learned during my master's studies. I also learned new things, that Chicago style is also referred to as the Turabian style, and that there were significant differences between the British and the American English. Also, it

is important I use the template, cite and reference correctly to avoid plagiarism and I must be consistent in my use of language and reference style.

REFERENCES

EUCLID University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.